

Teachers' Well-being and Work Performance

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Abstract

This study investigated the levels of well-being, and work performance among public school teachers in one district of a medium-sized division in a highly urbanized city in Negros Island Region, Philippines, during the School Year 2023–2024. Anchored on Seligman's PERMA model, the study examined teachers' positive emotion, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment, alongside the reported performance ratings. A descriptive research design was employed, involving 223 teachers across seven elementary and six secondary schools representing both urban and semi urban contexts. Findings revealed very high levels of well-being in positive emotion, engagement, and meaning, and high levels in relationships and accomplishment. Teachers' performance for the preceding year was rated outstanding across groups. No significant relationships were found between well-being and

work performance, suggesting that teachers maintain strong performance regardless of their personal well-being levels. Significant differences were observed only in the well-being domains of relationships and meaning when grouped by teaching level, and in work performance when grouped by level handled. Overall, the results underscore the resilience of Filipino public school teachers, who sustain high motivation and strong performance despite systemic challenges such as large class sizes, resource limitations, and administrative demands. While performance remains consistently high, the absence of direct links between well being, and performance highlights the need for institutional interventions that nurture relational well being, strengthen meaning-making, and prevent long-term burnout.

Keywords: *Teacher Well-being, Work Performance, PERMA Model, Public School Teachers, Filipino Teacher Resilience*

INTRODUCTION

The role of public school teachers in the Philippines extends beyond delivering instruction; they are pivotal in shaping learners' academic, emotional, and social development. Large class sizes, significant administrative work, scarce resources, frequent curriculum changes, and increased accountability requirements are just a few of the significant issues facing the nation's teachers. Due to these variables, teaching in the Philippine public education system is among the most demanding jobs (EDCOM 2, 2025; Idinsight, 2025). Teachers' well-being is further affected by the ongoing learning crisis, characterized by

pervasive learning gaps and resource constraints, including the ongoing absence of textbooks in many public schools (EDCOM 2, 2025).

Given these challenges, teacher well-being is critical to both individual job satisfaction and institutional effectiveness. Research demonstrates that teachers with higher levels of well-being tend to be more engaged and motivated, thereby being more productive; this, in turn, leads to better student outcomes and fosters a favorable school climate (Keller et al, 2024). On the contrary, low well-being levels lead to burnout, absenteeism, and attrition, a double blow to the institution's education quality (Keller et al., 2024; Wong, 2020)

Seligman (2011) proposed that the PERMA theory should be used to better understand and support teacher well-being. It includes five interconnected components: Positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment. New studies that apply the PERMA model in educational contexts confirm its usability for fostering teacher well-being and practical teaching (Fitzsimons, Boag, & Smith, 2025). Positive Emotions maintain psychological and physical health; engagement encourages active participation and job satisfaction; relationships bring about a supportive classroom environment; meaning gives purpose to teaching; and accomplishment increases motivation and professional fulfillment.

To provide empirical support for professional development initiatives, this study aims to investigate these relationships among public school teachers. The results are anticipated to foster a more resilient and motivated teaching workforce by encouraging a culture of well-being and care, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes amid the nation's persistent educational challenges

Current State of Knowledge

A thorough understanding of teachers' well-being in the Philippines includes more than just personal health. It also covers teachers' skills in handling challenging or sensitive situations in schools. Filipino school leaders play a key role in creating and running wellness programs that support teachers' emotional, physical, social, and professional needs. These programs aim to build positive attitudes, encourage healthy habits, and promote professional growth by consulting with stakeholders and forming specialized committees (Ortillo & Ancho, 2021).

With the help of these coping strategies, wellness programs in different districts across the Philippines highlight the importance of mental health, stress management, and developing quality teaching resources. Mental health is now recognized as a key part of teacher well-being, affecting both productivity and teaching effectiveness. Improvements in teacher performance may come from focusing on mental health, getting enough sleep, practicing mindfulness, exercising, and building personal management skills (Jimenez, 2021; Gerza, 2024).

Approaches developed in the Philippines show that positive change is possible through programs that are culturally sensitive and tailored to local needs. By combining health and wellness, stress management, sleep hygiene, and professional development programs with input from stakeholders, schools can create environments where teachers thrive instead of just coping with problems. So far, teacher performance in the Philippine context is seen as a multidimensional construct influenced by professional competencies and work conditions, and as a complex concept shaped by professional skills, working conditions, and national standards. According to Abulon (2014), effective teaching involves a mix of personal qualities, teaching knowledge, subject knowledge, and reflection. Heavy workloads and extra administrative tasks can also affect how well teachers perform (Tarraya, 2023). The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) define teacher performance across several areas, including content knowledge, teaching skills,

understanding student diversity, and ongoing professional development, all of which are based on adaptability and lifelong learning (Pedro & Reyes, 2023).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was grounded in two foundational theories that provide a strong framework for understanding the dynamics between teachers' well-being, and work performance. These are the PERMA Theory of Well-being developed by Martin Seligman (2011), and the **Job Performance Theory** developed by John Campbell (1990).

To begin with, the five fundamental components of human flourishing—positive emotion, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment—are outlined in the PERMA Theory of Well-Being, a thorough paradigm in positive psychology (Seligman, 2011). It is a detailed guide for well-being, but it is based on individualistic principles and is Western-centric. Relationship harmony, family ties, community involvement, and spirituality- concepts found in Sikolohiyang Pilipino, such as *kapwa* and *pakikiramdam* are key components of Filipino well-being. Therefore, when used in the Philippine context, PERMA has cultural limitations. Spiritual well-being is a complementary perspective, recognizing the significant role that faith plays in Filipino life. Filipino spirituality encompasses faith-based hope (*pag-asa*), moral character (*pagpapakatao*), and dependence on God (*bahala na*). By capturing aspects of meaning that PERMA does not capture, this improves the theoretical framework.

Finally, work performance is viewed as an individual-level variable by John P. Campbell's Job Performance Theory (1990), which focuses on actions that an individual takes that are pertinent to organizational objectives. By defining performance as behaviors or actions within an individual's control—whether observable acts or mental processes such as decision-making or problem-solving—Campbell distinguishes it from outcomes. Sales revenue is one example of an outcome influenced by individual performance and external factors beyond the employee's control. Campbell further stresses that work performance should be goal-oriented and aligned with the position's primary duties, excluding activities not tied to organizational goals. He also suggests that job performance is multifaceted, encompassing non-task-specific actions (such as training others) and task-specific behaviors (such as core duties). This paradigm emphasizes how knowledge, skills, motivation, and behavior contribute to performance, a complex construct that determines how effectively a person performs their job (Campbell, 1990).

Two interconnected theories serve as the foundation for this study. The PERMA model offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment influence teachers' overall well-being. And, Campbell's theory situates work performance within the context of goal-directed behavior, influenced by knowledge, skills, and motivation—all of which are affected by a teacher's overall health and ability to cope with stress.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to examine the link between the teachers' well-being and work performance in public secondary schools in one district of a medium-sized division of a highly urbanized city in Negros Island Region during the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, and level handled? What is the level of teachers' well-being in terms of the areas positive emotion, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment? What is the level of work performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables? Is there a significant difference in the level of teachers' well-being when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables? Is there a significant difference in the level of

teachers' work performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables? And, is there a significant relationship between the levels of teachers' well-being and work performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design to determine the levels of teachers' well-being, and work performance in one of the districts in a medium-sized division in a highly urbanized city in Negros Island Region, Philippines, during the School Year 2023-2024. The methodological approach of descriptive study design, according to Enago (2023), is to observe, characterize, and record the traits, behaviors, or circumstances of a particular population or phenomenon without changing any factors. Its primary goal is to provide a comprehensive and accurate picture of the subject under study by identifying patterns, frequencies, trends, and relationships within the data. Descriptive design is appropriate for this study because it aims to discover what prevails in the present condition or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. As part of the scientific method, the design entails monitoring and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any influence.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 223 public school teachers from a total population of 529. Since the number of respondents is significant, a stratified random sampling technique was used, with Cochran's formula (Cochran, 1977), a widely used method for estimating sample size in survey research when targeting proportions, to determine the sample size. Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling technique that divides a population into distinct subgroups, known as strata, based on shared characteristics such as age, gender, income, or education level. Stratified random sampling was used, dividing the population into homogenous strata to ensure proportional representation and increased precision (Thomas, 2020).

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their school.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

School	Population (N)	Sample (n)	Percentage (%)
A	64	27	12.10
B	59	25	11.15
C	22	9	4.16
D	15	6	2.84
E	37	15	6.99
F	63	26	11.91
G	26	11	4.92
H	57	24	10.78
I	35	15	6.62
J	56	24	10.59
K	30	13	5.67
L	35	15	6.62

M	30	13	5.67
TOTAL	529	223	100

Instrument

This study utilized a self-made survey questionnaire to determine the teachers' well-being, while secondary data on their work performance. The instrument consisted of two parts: Part I gathered respondents' profile information, including age, civil status, and level handled, while Part II constituted the bulk of the questionnaire and focused on the five well-being components of Seligman's PERMA Theory: positive emotion, engagement, relationship, meaning, and accomplishment. There were six items per component, yielding 30 statements for respondents to rate. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 5 (Always) to 1 (Never). And, the work performance was based on their IPCRF for SY 2022-2023.

The validity of the instrument was established with five expert validators who are recognized education professionals, including Chief Education Supervisors and Public Schools District Supervisors within the division. Validation followed the criteria of Good and Scates, with interpretation ranges from Poor to Excellent. The instrument obtained a validation mean of 4.80, interpreted as Excellent, indicating high validity.

Reliability was determined using Cronbach's alpha to assess internal consistency. A pilot test was conducted among 30 teachers who were not part of the actual respondents and were drawn from the same district. The teachers' well-being yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.969, interpreted as Excellent, confirming that the research instrument is reliable.

Data Gathering and Procedure

After administering the validity and reliability tests, and upon approval of the schools division superintendent, the questionnaires were administered to the target respondents. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The encoded data were processed using SPSS.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 to 3 employed a descriptive analytical scheme, using frequency counts and percentages as statistical tools to assess the profile of respondents, mean to assess the level of teachers' well-being across the five areas and level of work performance. Objectives 4 and 5 utilized a comparative analytical scheme, applying the Mann-Whitney U test to determine significant differences in the levels of teachers' well-being and work performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Lastly, objective 6 used Spearman rho to examine the significant relationship between the levels of teacher' well-being and their work performance.

Ethical Consideration

The study strictly observed ethical research standards by ensuring the protection of respondents' rights and welfare throughout the research process. The researcher secured written informed consent from the respondents prior to data collection. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their right to withdraw at any time

without penalty. To minimize potential harm, the confidentiality of all responses was guaranteed, and the anonymity of the respondents was maintained during data gathering, analysis, and reporting. Moreover, the study complied with the provisions of Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which mandates the lawful, fair, and secure processing of personal and sensitive information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Respondents

Table 2. Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 41 years old)	121	54.30
	Older (41 years old and above)	102	45.70
	Total	223	100
Civil Status	Single	68	30.50
	Married	155	69.50
	Total	223	100
Level Handled	1st Key Stage (Kindergarten – Grade 3)	74	33.20
	2nd Key Stage (Grade 4 - Grade 6)	67	30.00
	3rd Key Stage (Grade 7 - Grade 10)	82	36.80
	Total	223	100

Table 2 shows the age, civil status, and teaching level of the 223 teachers who responded to the survey. Of these, 121 (54.30%) are under 41 years old and 102 (45.70%) are 41 or older. This means the group includes both younger and more experienced teachers in nearly equal numbers. Most of the teachers are married (155 or 69.50%), while 68 (30.50%) are single. This means many teachers balance their jobs with family life, which could affect how they view their workload and work-life balance. The teachers are spread fairly evenly across teaching levels. The biggest group teaches Key Stage 3 (Grades 7–10) with 82 teachers (36.80%), followed by Key Stage 1 (K–3) with 74 (33.20%), and Key Stage 2 (Grades 4–6) with 67 (30.00%). This shows all levels are well represented, with a few more teachers in the higher grades.

Table 3. Level of Teachers' Well-being in the Area of Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. am motivated to perform my tasks.	4.86	Very High Level
2. have a sense of accomplishment after completing my work.	4.76	Very High Level
3. am excited about the projects and tasks I am working on.	4.65	Very High Level
4. feel relaxed and stress-free while working.	4.08	High Level
5. am happy with the work-life balance.	4.29	High Level
6. feel confident in my abilities to perform my job.	4.85	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.58	Very High Level

The data in Table 3 demonstrates teachers' well-being in terms of positive emotion, captured through six specific indicators. The overall mean score is 4.58, which indicates a "Very High Level." From the items, Item 1: "I am motivated to perform my tasks" had the highest mean of 4.86, which can be interpreted as a Very High Level. On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean is Item 4: "I feel relaxed and stress-free while working," which was scored at 4.08 and was interpreted as a High Level.

The lower rating on feeling relaxed and stress-free while working has important implications. Even with high motivation, confidence, and a sense of achievement, a good number of teachers still seem to be under some level of stress or pressure from their everyday duties. This could stem from overwhelming workloads, including repetitive administrative work, teaching large classes, or the emotional toll that teaching exacts. This is also noted as observed to teachers while checking the two sets of summative papers, though responding to printing and division encoding requests; the teacher skipped recess to meet a noon cutoff; and verbalized, "*Kapoy pero sige lang*" (Tiring, but I'll keep going.) "*Motivated gid ko, pero ang reports kag encoding ang nagadugang sang pressure*" (I'm really motivated, but the reports and encoding are adding to the pressure.)

These findings reinforce the study by Bauer et al. (2023), which found that even well-engaged teachers can experience emotional exhaustion when they lack sufficient mechanisms to manage stress. However, Noblezada et al. (2025) also emphasized that high motivation does not necessarily equate to low stress levels, as educators often face workload pressures and emotional demands. This aligns with the present finding that the lowest-rated item is feeling relaxed and stress-free ($M = 4.08$), indicating that teachers may still experience strain despite being highly engaged and fulfilled in their work.

Table 4. Level of Well-being of Teachers in Engagement

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I/my...</i>		
1. am connected to the mission and values of the school and the Department.	4.72	Very High Level
2. have opportunities to make a meaningful impact.	4.85	Very High Level
3. am learning and growing professionally.	4.92	Very High Level
4. have a clear understanding of my role and responsibilities.	4.92	Very High Level
5. skills and strengths are being utilized.	4.63	Very High Level
6. feel engaged in my work.	4.78	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.80	Very High Level

In terms of Engagement, as shown in Table 4, teacher well-being was measured using six key indicators. The average value across was 4.80, which is classified as a Very High Level. Among them, Items 3, "I am learning and growing professionally," and Item 4, "I have a clear understanding of my role and responsibilities," both had the highest mean of 4.92, interpreted as a Very High Level. On the other hand, Item 5, "My skills and strengths are being utilized," had the lowest mean of 4.63, although it was still classified as a Very High Level.

The comparatively low score in the use of skills and competencies suggests possible underutilization of teachers' full potential. Although educators appreciate the responsibilities that come with a professional career and are engaged in professional development, many do not feel that their talents, refined skills, or distinct professional niches are valued or utilized effectively in their work. This type of underutilization poses problems for motivation and job satisfaction in the long run, as well as for retention, particularly among highly skilled educators who expect opportunities to engage meaningfully beyond routine tasks.

These findings align with recent research work. Collie (2023) emphasized that meaningful teacher participation is enhanced when respondents feel that their strengths are recognized and utilized within the context of the school's operations.

Table 5. Level of Well-being of Teachers in Relationships

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I/my ...</i>		
1. have positive working relationships with my colleagues and superiors.	4.49	High Level
2. feel that there is a sense of teamwork and collaboration among colleagues.	4.13	High Level
3. have positive working relationships with external stakeholders of our school.	4.61	Very High Level
4. am able to communicate effectively with my colleagues and superiors.	4.49	High Level
5. opinions and suggestions are valued and taken into consideration.	4.43	High Level
6. feel that conflicts and disagreements are handled constructively.	3.95	High Level
Overall Mean	4.35	High Level

Table 5 summarizes teachers' well-being regarding Relationships, as analyzed using six specific indicators, including the mean value. Considering the data, the overall mean is 4.35, which is a High Level. Among the items, Item 3, "I have positive working relationships with external stakeholders of our school," had the highest mean value of 4.61, indicating a very High Level. In contrast to that, Item 6: "I feel that conflicts and disagreements are handled constructively," which was scored at 3.95, was relatively lower than others, but still perceived to be a High Level.

The lowest-rated item directly indicates a potential area for improvement. Teachers reported generally positive working relationships, but much lower ratings for constructive conflict resolution suggest that interpersonal tensions or disagreements are not always handled in ways that foster understanding and growth. This could lead to unresolved issues, a lack of collaboration, or distrust among faculty. This implies a need for more formalized procedures to address conflict, open communication around conflict, and training in communication and media. Also, this result is experiential: a Grading deadline confusion escalated in a department Group Chat, where two teachers used ALL CAPS, one left the chat, and the issue was resolved only after the School Head intervened. This pattern reflects the absence of structured protocols for staff conflict. DepEd's Child Protection Policy (DO 40 s.2012) expects safe, respectful climates, where schools can adapt CPC/restorative practices for adult disputes.

These findings were similar to those of Reyes, Asuncion, and Castro (2021), who demonstrated that Filipino teachers were highly collegial but had gaps in their schools' conflict-resolution and emotional-support mechanisms.

Table 6. The Level of Well-being of Teachers in Meaning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I/my ...</i>		
1. work is meaningful and fulfilling.	4.81	Very High Level
2. work is aligned with my personal values and beliefs.	4.62	Very High Level
3. work is making a positive impact on the community.	4.72	Very High Level
4. am using my skills and abilities to their fullest potential.	4.62	Very High Level
5. am being challenged and learning new things through my work.	4.65	Very High Level
6. am able to express my creativity and innovation.	4.36	High Level
Overall Mean	4.63	Very High Level

Table 6 indicates that teachers are in a state of well-being in terms of Meaning, which examines how teachers view the aim and importance of their work. The overall mean is 4.63, which is interpreted as "Very High Level." The highest-scoring item is 1, "My work is meaningful and fulfilling," with a mean score of 4.81, indicating a Very High Level. Item 6: "I am able to express my creativity and innovation" scored the lowest mean of 4.36, indicating a high level.

This is true, as observed in Grade 7 Science, a project-based learning task was initially planned to promote active student engagement. However, due to limitations in printing and instructional materials, as well as conflicts with the scheduled periodical tests, the activity was cancelled. As an alternative, the teacher shifted to direct instruction. During implementation, students were observed to be less participative, with a noticeable decline in enthusiasm and engagement compared to earlier sessions in which interactive strategies were anticipated.

Low scores in creativity and innovation indicate that, although teachers value the purpose of their work, they may lack the independence and freedom to adopt new procedures, ideas, or teaching methodologies. The restrictions regarding experimentation may come from rigid curricular requirements or standardized testing pressures, both of which are further complicated by several administrative limits on experimentation. For some, a lack of creative expression may lead to failure in exciting and training them further in the field. Additionally, while teachers consistently demonstrate a strong sense of professional purpose, their capacity for instructional creativity is often constrained by limited time and resources.

Research in the Philippines validates the claim that teachers' work can be full of meaning; however, institutional constraints often prevent the implementation of creative and innovative practices. In one study, Alfonso and Andres (2020) found that teachers derive personal satisfaction from the profession due to the perceived social value and moral purpose associated with it. However, they observed that bureaucratic policies and strict adherence to standardized curricula often inhibit innovation in teaching methods.

Table 7. Level of Well-being of Teachers in Accomplishment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I ...</i>		
1. feel that I have accomplished the goals I set for myself.	4.65	Very High Level
2. am making progress in my work.	4.78	Very High Level
3. am meeting or even exceeding the expectations set for me.	4.59	Very High Level
4. am being recognized and rewarded for my achievements.	4.11	High Level
5. am given opportunities to take on new and challenging projects.	4.48	High Level
6. feel that I am being given the resources and support I need to achieve my goals.	4.30	High Level
Overall Mean	4.49	High Level

Table 7 illustrates teachers' well-being across the accomplishment area, measured by six indicators. The overall mean score is 4.49, which falls under the category of "High Level." The highest-scoring item is Item 2, "I am making progress in my work," with a mean of 4.78 and a classification of "Very High Level." On the other hand, Item 4, "I am being recognized and rewarded for my achievements," scored lowest, with a mean of 4.11, despite being classified as High Level.

This result is particularly notable, as a teacher's literacy routine demonstrated a significant impact, moving 8 out of 12 struggling readers to the instructional level within a span of 6 weeks. This achievement was shared during the Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. Still, it was neither formally documented in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) nor supported by an official citation. In a reflective check-in conversation, the teacher remarked: "*Okay lang wala award, pero maayo tani makita sa IPCRF*" ("It's fine without an award, but it would be better if this could be recognized in the IPCRF"). In the same manner, the relatively lower score on recognition and reward indicates a notable discrepancy between the full contribution of a teacher and how the school recognizes it. While teachers may experience personal growth and effective goal attainment, a lack of adequate and appropriate external validation can leave them feeling underappreciated or disregarded. This can, over time, negatively impact motivation, job satisfaction, and retention, particularly among high-performing teachers.

These findings support recent studies that emphasize the importance of recognition in improving teachers' well-being. Cruz and Arias (2021) claim that teachers' motivation and sense of professional value are significantly increased when they receive recognition from school administration. Similarly, Kim and Yang (2022) found that to maintain high levels of engagement and organizational commitment, intrinsic accomplishments must be supplemented by external rewards and feedback.

Table 8. Level of Work Performance of Teachers

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.65	Outstanding
	Older	4.68	Outstanding
Civil Status	Single	4.66	Outstanding
	Married	4.67	Outstanding
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	4.65	Outstanding
	2nd Key Stage	4.74	Outstanding
	3rd Key Stage	4.61	Outstanding

Table 8 presents the figures for work performance when teachers were categorized by age, civil status, and level handled. When grouped by age, younger and older teachers were performing excellently, with mean scores of 4.65 and 4.68, respectively. This implies that the quality of teaching is not influenced by experience or age and, thus, teachers at varying stages of their careers would be performing at equally high levels

The performance of teachers grouped by civil status shows consistency: single teachers attained a mean score of 4.66, while married teachers achieved a mean score of 4.67, both indicating outstanding performance. This close comparison shows that conditions in private life, such as being married, do not detract from teachers' professional efficiency.

Level handled is yet another division in which outstanding performance is consistently achieved across the board. Teachers at the 2nd Key Stage registered the highest mean score of 4.74, followed by the 1st Key Stage, with a mean score of 4.65, and lastly, the 3rd Key Stage, with a mean score of 4.61. Such a slight difference could indicate variation in curriculum demands or in student motivation levels across different key stages. Still, it does not hinder the teachers' overall high performance.

These results also align with those of Catarus and Guanzon (2025), which demonstrate that teachers consistently delivered outstanding work performance regardless of demographic factors such as age, civil status, and sex. Their studies have shown that, in general, performance ratings for public school teachers were very satisfactory, and that the sex and civil status of teachers had no bearing on their work outcomes.

Furthermore, these results align with Maculada and Guanzon (2024) who found that teachers maintain high performance no matter their demographic background, with professionalism and commitment playing important roles. And, Doromal et al. (2024) also showed that teachers perform well even when their work situations and workloads change, showing their adaptability and resilience.

Table 9. Difference in the Level of Well-being of Teachers in the area of Positive Emotion

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	111.09	6060.500		0.814	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	113.08					
Civil Status	Single	68	111.59	5242.000		0.949	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	155	112.18					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	113.76	5.298		0.071	0.05	Not Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	124.19					
	3rd Key Stage	82	100.45					

Table 9 presents an analysis of differences in well-being levels among teachers in the area of positive emotion, grouped by age, civil status, and level of responsibility.

Results indicate no statistically significant difference among the groups for any of the variables. Specifically, for the variable positive emotion, the Mann-Whitney U test comparing younger teachers (mean rank = 111.09) and older teachers (mean rank = 113.08) yielded a p-value of 0.814, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Similarly, the civil status groups single (mean rank = 111.59) and married (mean rank = 112.18) did not differ significantly ($p = 0.949$). Although there was some variation in mean rank (the 2nd Key Stage had the highest mean rank of 124.19, whilst the 3rd Key Stage had the lowest mean rank of 100.45), the Kruskal-Wallis test for the variable level taught and positive emotion gave a p-value of 0.071, suggesting it was not significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference between the level of teachers' well-being in the area of positive emotion when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables" is hereby accepted.

These results suggest that teachers' positive emotional well-being remains consistent across various demographic characteristics, including age, marital status, and teaching level. The uniformity may reflect either generally supportive working conditions or effective coping mechanisms among teachers across the different groups.

This aligns with the results of Botona and Baguio (2025), which indicate that teachers' positive emotions and well-being are generally stable across demographic variables when adequate stress management strategies are in place. This emphasizes the need to develop further such a strategy to maintain and sustain teacher well-being.

Table 10. Difference in the Level of Well-being of Teachers in the area of Engagement

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	110.52	5992.50		0.680	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	113.75					
Civil Status	Single	68	115.09	5060.00		0.599	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	155	110.65					
Level Handled	1st Stage	Key	74	118.14	4.80	0.090	0.05	Not Significant
	2nd Stage	Key	67	118.90				
	3rd Stage	Key	82	100.82				

Table 10 examines differences in well-being among teachers by engagement, age, marital status, and level of responsibility.

The outcomes and results analyzed above show that there were no statistically significant differences across these variables. In terms of age, a Mann-Whitney U test was performed; younger teachers had a mean rank of 110.52, while older teachers had a mean rank of 113.75. The p-value was 0.680, which is above the 0.05 significance level; hence, there was no significant difference in engagement by age. Similarly, the comparison between single (mean rank = 115.09) and married teachers (mean rank = 110.65) showed no significant difference ($p = 0.599$). The teaching levels produced a p-value of 0.090 with the Kruskal-Wallis H test, which is not significant at the 0.05 level, despite the highest mean rank being for the 2nd Key Stage (118.90) and the lowest for the 3rd Key Stage (100.82). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference between the level of teachers' well-being in the area of engagement when grouped and compared according to the variables" is hereby accepted.

Hence, it is concluded that regardless of age, civil status, or teaching level, teachers' engagement levels remain unchanged. This may have been due to a commonality of values of the teaching profession or engagement strategies that work well and have been efficiently used by all groups.

This explanation, further supported by the research of Martínez et al. (2023), concludes that emotional stability and efficient emotion regulation are the primary predictors of psychological well-being and engagement among teachers, which again highlights how engagement can be uniform among teachers of different ages and social statuses.

Table 11. Difference in the Level of Well-being of Teachers in the area of Relationships

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	109.33	5848.500		0.498		Not Significant
	Older	102	115.16					
Civil Status	Single	68	107.93	4993.000		0.529		Not Significant
	Married	155	113.79					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	119.91		12.231	0.002	0.05	Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	126.88					
	3rd Key Stage	82	92.70					

Table 11 presents differences in teachers' well-being in the area of relationships, grouped by age, civil status, and level of responsibility.

In the realm of relationship well-being, younger teachers (mean rank = 109.33) and older teachers (mean rank = 115.16) showed no significant difference, $p = 0.498$. Similarly, single teachers (mean rank = 107.93) and married teachers (mean rank = 113.79) also showed no significant difference, $p = 0.529$. Thus, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ well-being in the area of relationship when grouped and compared according to the variables age and civil status” is hereby accepted.” The relationship well-being was, however, statistically significantly different across groups based on levels handled (Kruskal-Wallis $H=12.231$; $p=0.002$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ well-being in the area of relationship when grouped and compared according to the variable level handled” is hereby “rejected.”

The 2nd Key Stage teachers had the highest mean rank (126.88), followed by the 1st Key Stage teachers (119.91), while the 3rd Key Stage teachers had the lowest mean rank (92.70). The 2nd Key Stage teachers enjoy better relationship-related well-being than those of the 1st and 3rd Key Stages.

Thus, the kinds of positive relationships that teachers handling lower key stages can maintain may be influenced by the interactions they share with younger students: nurturing, consistent, and emotionally engaging. Furthermore, these stages typically establish a classroom environment that fosters stronger teacher-student relationships through regular routines and close supervision. Early and middle levels of education not only encourage collaborative teaching but also involve structured team support that benefits collegial relationships and the development of a teacher community.

In contrast, teachers of upper grades, who focus more on subject mastery and independent work, typically find themselves in content-heavy, exam-oriented situations that offer little room for substantive relational engagement with students and colleagues. Apart from influencing the relational aspect of well-being, the developmental maturity of older students might also lead the teacher-student interaction to become more formal or distant.

This study thus corroborates Collie and Martin's (2023) findings that positive teacher-student relationships are linked to higher levels of teacher vitality, engagement, and professional growth. Teachers who reported strong connections with their students early in the term sustained high levels of well-being throughout the term.

Table 12. Difference in the Level of Well-being of Teachers in the area of Meaning

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	111.17	6070.000		0.823	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	112.99					
Civil Status	Single	68	112.62	5228.000		0.920	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	155	111.73					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	118.91	7.421		0.024	0.05	Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	122.01					
	3rd Key Stage	82	97.59					

Table 12 presents the differences in the level of well-being of teachers in the area of meaning when grouped by age, civil status, and level of responsibility.

No significant differences were found in age or civil status. Specifically, younger teachers (mean rank = 111.17) and older teachers (mean rank = 112.99) showed no significant difference in their sense of meaning at work ($p = 0.823$). Likewise, single teachers (mean rank = 112.62) and married teachers (mean rank = 111.73) also exhibit no significant difference, with a p-value of 0.920. On the other hand, when analyzed across the level handled by the teachers, a significant difference was found in the sense of meaning (Kruskal-Wallis $H = 7.421$, $p = 0.024$). Teachers of the 2nd Key Stage held the highest mean rank of 122.01, followed closely by those in the 1st Key Stage with 118.91, while those in the 3rd Key Stage came away with the lowest mean rank of 97.59.

Therefore, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ well-being in the area of meaning when grouped and compared according to the variables age and civil status” is hereby accepted.” But, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ well-being in the area of meaning when grouped and compared according to the variable level handled” is hereby “rejected.”

The analysis revealed that lower- and middle-key-stage teachers appear to experience a stronger sense of meaning in their work than those in the upper key stage. One possible explanation is that early and middle-grade teachers play a crucial role in shaping their students' development, thereby strengthening the perceived purpose and fulfillment. Emphasis in these levels is placed on emotional, social, and basic academic development, where teachers can observe and make a tangible difference in student growth.

Moreover, the lower levels of teaching typically allow for a more holistic interaction with students, cultivating closer relationships and shaping a united classroom environment. Compared to higher key stages, teachers may find that their shared time is being sliced, content-heavy, and pressured to hold students accountable on standardized assessments, all of which shift away from relational and purposeful pursuits. Hence, all these things become a procedure that is not very beneficial from a personal perspective.

Supporting these findings, a study by Steger et al. (2017) also showed that a strong sense of meaning at work among teachers is closely associated with job satisfaction and teachers' well-being, and that this sense might differ across job roles and contexts.

Table 13. Difference in the Level of Well-being of Teachers in the Area of Accomplishment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	110.80	6026.000		0.756		Not Significant
	Older	102	113.42					
Civil Status	Single	68	109.96	5131.500		0.748		Not Significant
	Married	155	112.89					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	106.23	0.937		0.626	0.05	Not Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	114.75					
	3rd Key Stage	82	114.96					

Table 13 presents the differences in the level of well-being of teachers in the area of accomplishment when grouped by age, civil status, and level of responsibility.

Young teachers (mean rank = 110.80) do not differ significantly from older teachers (mean rank = 113.42) in their sense of accomplishment (p -value = 0.756). Similarly, single teachers (mean rank = 109.96) do not differ significantly from married teachers (mean rank = 112.89) in their sense of accomplishment (p -value = 0.748). Levels handled also do not result in a significant difference in accomplishment between teachers in 1st, 2nd, and 3rd Key Stages, as determined by the Kruskal-Wallis test (p -value = 0.626). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference between the level of teachers' well-being in the area of accomplishment when grouped and compared according to the variables" is hereby accepted.

This implies that people of different ages, civil statuses, and teaching grades share similar experiences in achieving goals, receiving recognition for their work, and progressing professionally. Consistently moderate to high levels of accomplishment are reported across these variables, suggesting that supports, school culture, and performance expectations are implemented uniformly regardless of background. Such uniformity may result from universal professional development opportunities, common institutional objectives, or uniform practices in performance evaluation across schools.

Echoing these results, recent systematic reviews indicate that teachers' well-being, including their sense of accomplishment, is more strongly shaped by personal capabilities (such as self-efficacy and coping strategies) than by demographic factors. Collie et al. (2023) emphasize that teacher self-efficacy strongly predicts occupational well-being and accomplishment, thus buffering against stress or burnout among heterogeneous groups of teachers.

Table 14. Comparative Analysis on the Level of Teachers' Work Performance

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	105.43	5376.500		0.097		Not Significant
	Older	102	119.79					
Civil Status	Single	68	108.15	5008.500		0.555		Not Significant
	Married	155	113.69					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	107.70	33.953		0.000	0.05	Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	147.88					
	3rd Key Stage	82	86.56					

Table 14 displays differences in teachers' work performance levels across age, civil status, and handled level.

In terms of work performance, neither age nor civil status significantly affects teachers' performance. Younger teachers (mean rank = 105.43) and older teachers (mean rank = 119.79) did not differ significantly when performance was considered a variable ($p = 0.097$). The same holds for single teachers (mean rank = 108.15) and married teachers (mean rank = 113.69), with a p -value of 0.555. Significant differences were found between teachers handling different levels (Kruskal-Wallis $H = 33.953$, $p = 0.000$). Teachers working in the 2nd Key Stage had the highest mean rank (147.88), indicating better performance than those working in the 1st Key Stage (mean rank = 107.70) and the 3rd Key Stage (mean rank = 86.56).

Thus, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ work performance when grouped and compared according to the variables age and civil status” is hereby accepted.” However, the null hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ work performance when grouped and compared according to the variable level handled” is hereby “rejected.”

This suggests that demographic factors do not substantially influence how teachers deliver their work. However, a significant difference emerges when grouped by level handled. Second Key Stage teachers (Grades 4–6) achieved the highest mean rank (147.88), while Third Key Stage teachers (Grades 7–10) scored the lowest (86.56). This suggests that middle-grade teachers may feel more affirmed in their instructional outcomes, while secondary teachers face greater challenges, including exam preparation, managing adolescent learners, and stricter accountability measures.

The 2nd Key Stage teachers may enjoy a balance between foundational instruction and student independence. At this stage, students are sufficiently capable of working independently with the content provided by their teachers. Therefore, teachers can employ a broader range of instructional strategies, monitor progress more effectively, and assess performance indicators more accurately. Correspondingly, curricular expectations at this stage may better reflect measurable performance outcomes upon which professional development opportunities and recognition frameworks are based.

Conversely, 1st Key Stage teachers generally provide students with foundational skills, which may take time to exhibit definite and positive effects or results, negatively impacting perceived performance. On the other end of the spectrum, 3rd Key Stage teachers, who are often subject specialists across different grades, may face more content-heavy demands combined with administrative duties, reducing the time available for collaborative or integrative teaching approaches and thereby negatively impacting their performance ratings.

Consistent with Klassen and Chiu's (2020) research, teacher performance depends on teaching level, with middle-level teachers tending to report higher self-efficacy and performance, which may be linked to the developmental appropriateness of the curriculum and teacher-student relations.

Table 15. Relationship between the Level of Teachers' Well-being and Work Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Well-being	-0.014	0.837	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Work Performance				

The data presented in Table 15 suggest a very weak, negative correlation ($\rho = -0.014$) between teachers' well-being status and their work performance, although the $p < 0.05$ threshold was not met for testing. Given the p-value of 0.837, this relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states "there is no significant relationship between the levels of teachers' well-being and work performance" is hereby accepted.

This indicates that while teachers report high levels of both well-being and performance, the two variables do not statistically influence each other in this data set. In other words, outstanding work performance is sustained despite fluctuations in well-being, suggesting that teachers' professional commitment and sense of duty remain strong even when personal well-being is challenged.

The absence of a significant correlation highlights a critical issue: teachers may be overcompensating for stress or wellness concerns by prioritizing performance. While this demonstrates resilience, it also raises sustainability concerns. Schools should therefore strengthen wellness programs, counseling services, and workload management—not because performance is currently low, but to ensure that high performance can be sustained without compromising long-term health and morale.

An analysis of the study reveals that teacher well-being does not directly influence work performance. This may be attributed to Filipino teachers' deep vocational commitment and their often-calling-like view of teaching. They go on performing well even if their psychological health or emotional well-being is compromised because of stress, financial constraints, and sometimes a lack of institutional support. Additionally, this may be attributed to the culture of endurance, sacrifice, and dedication to learners that is instilled throughout the Philippine teaching community.

Contrary evidence was found in a prior study by Ahmed and Malik (2019), which found that both psychological empowerment and psychological well-being exert a significant positive influence on teachers' job performance. Furthermore, their findings revealed that psychological well-being partially mediated the relationship between empowerment and performance, indicating that when teachers feel psychologically empowered, their well-being improves, which, in turn, enhances their work performance.

Conclusion

The results show that teachers have very high levels of well-being, especially in positive emotion, engagement, and meaning. This suggests they are strongly motivated and find fulfillment in their work. While relationships and accomplishment are also high, they are a bit lower, pointing to possible needs for more support in social connection and recognition. Teachers manage stress well and show resilience, using steady coping strategies no matter their age, civil status, or teaching level.

Teachers continue to perform at a high level, and their age or civil status does not have much effect on their performance. However, performance does change depending on the teaching level, likely because each stage has different demands. Teacher well-being does not directly predict performance, which suggests that factors like professional commitment and what the institution expects may be more important.

Generally, the findings show that teachers are resilient and dedicated, keeping their performance high even with heavy workloads. Still, this raises questions about how sustainable this is in the long run, and it highlights the need for better support from institutions to protect teachers' well-being.

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